

Impact of Corporate Social Responsibility, Green Credit and Digitalisation on Bank Stability: A Case Study of Banks in Vietnam

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Abstract

Background: Social responsibility, green lending, and digital transformation are crucial to sustainable development and offer banks chances to increase their market competitiveness and operate sustainably. Moreover, green credit and digital transformation are inevitable, but coordination is needed between banks, the government, and related organizations to implement them successfully.

Objective: This study examines the relationship between green credit, digitalization, and bank stability in Vietnam.

Methodology: The authors employed moments quantile regression (MMQR) to elucidate varied effects across varying levels of bank stability. The research used a panel dataset of Vietnamese commercial banks from 2010 to 2022. Data were obtained from the annual reports of the State Bank and banks.

Result: The results showed that each corporate social responsibility (CSR) component has different dimensions, such as shareholders, employees, customers, government, social, community, and environmental responsibility, which have different impacts on bank stability. Digital transformation is an essential solution to achieve sustainable development goals and opens up opportunities to help banks improve their competitiveness in the market.

Conclusion: There is a nonlinear relationship where higher levels of CSR engagement are associated with lower bank stability, but this negative effect diminishes at higher levels of CSR. In addition to using digital tools, green credit is essential in successfully implementing green programs to ensure banking sustainability.

Unique Contribution: The study has shown that CSR's positive impact on stability is more substantial for state-owned commercial banks and that the benefits of CSR may diminish during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Key Recommendation: Investments in digitalisation initially reduce bank stability due to high technology costs, but the interaction of digitalisation with CSR optimises efficiency and reduces information asymmetry, promoting long-term stability.

Keywords: CSR; Green credit; digitalization; bank stability; and MMQR

Introduction

Banking management strategies prioritise sustainable development in the face of a fragile global economy and climate change (Andaiyani et al., 2023). Banks promote sustainable economic activity through loan and investment policies and provide economic capital. The banking industry in Vietnam has grown with international integration, creating opportunities and problems.

Corporate social responsibility (CSR), green credit, and digitalization drive banking industry sustainability (Wang et al., 2023). Many global studies have demonstrated that these variables can reduce operational risks, increase brand reputation, and create long-term value, improving bank stability (Zhou et al., 2022). The combined and measured effects of CSR, green credit, and digitisation on bank stability in Vietnam have not been investigated. This paper fills a research gap by describing how these fundamental elements affect bank financial stability in developing economies.

This study uses stakeholder theory and the resource-based firm view. According to stakeholder theory, banks should consider the interests of customers, workers, and communities when making decisions. The resource-based concept holds that banks can achieve a competitive edge using their CSR, green credit, and digital technology capabilities (Yongjie & Jin, 2023). Banking CSR comprises social, environmental, consumer, and shareholder responsibility. Effective CSR may reduce information asymmetry, boost consumer trust, and improve risk management. Green Credit also finances renewable energy, sustainable agriculture, and waste treatment initiatives. Although the State Bank of Vietnam encourages green credit, its application in the banking system is limited. Digitalization improves operating efficiency, reduces costs, and improves risk forecasting for banks. Rapid digital transformation raises concerns about data security and investment costs (Adikaram, 2023; Nga & Tam, 2024).

Mixed results have been found in developed market research on CSR and bank performance. CSR has been shown to improve bank performance in particular research but not others. CSR's influence has been studied separately without considering its linkages with other sustainable banking practices. Thus, the study's objective is to examine the impact of corporate social responsibility, green credit, and digitalization on bank stability in Vietnam. These ideas were used to propose strategies to support a more stable and sustainable banking system.

Theoretical Framework

Corporate Social Responsibility and Bank Stability

The study summarizes its findings on corporate social responsibility, green lending, digitization, and bank stability in this part. Banks must now consider the interests of consumers, employees, and communities in their decision-making, making corporate social responsibility (CSR) more significant (Neitzert & Petras, 2022). Mixed results have been found in empirical studies on CSR and bank performance. CSR has been shown to improve bank performance in specific research but not in others (Adikaram, 2023). Current research reveals that CSR can significantly affect bank stability. Neitzert and Petras (2022) found that CSR reduces bank risk. Bank liquidity can improve with CSR. Stakeholder theory implies that CSR programs can increase deposits and loans, enhancing banks' financial stability.

Green Credit and Bank Stability

Green credit is banking that supports and lends to green projects and enterprises to promote sustainable development. The literature suggests that green credit can affect bank stability and performance. According to developed market studies, green financing increases bank profitability and reduces credit risk. Gaudio et al. (2022) found that banks' green lending trend and cautious lending practices can help the green transition and increase bank profitability. Zhou et al. (2022) found that China's green lending policy reduced banks' climate-related financial risks. Emerging market research on green finance and bank stability is scarce. Some studies have shed light. Higher bank capital means more loans, suggesting that banks' capital levels may influence green credit initiatives. Educational platforms and technical guidance can help banks assess environmental risks and opportunities in their green lending decisions.

Digitalisation and Bank Stability

Existing literature implies that digitalizing banking activities can affect bank stability and performance. Digitalisation involves integrating mobile banking, AI, and cloud computing into a bank's fundamental business activities (Andaiyani et al., 2023).

Bank digitalization improves operational efficiency, customer experience, and costs in developed markets, according to empirical studies (Wang et al., 2021). Digital transformation increased banks' operating skills, which can boost stability, according to Yongjie and Jin (2023). Research on digitisation and banking stability in emerging nations is scarce. Some studies have shed light. Digital banking improves the client experience, contentment, and loyalty, which boosts bank financial performance, according to Sugihyanto (2023). Studies stressed that the economic and banking industry must innovate using digital technology to communicate with customers (Chen et al., 2023; Galan & Tan, 2024). Based on the theoretical overview and research gaps, the paper develops the following hypotheses:

Hypothesis H1: CSR positively impacts banking stability in Vietnam, helping reduce credit risk and improve risk management efficiency.

Hypothesis H2: The impact of CSR on bank stability increases when combined with green credit.

Hypothesis H3: Digitalization plays a moderating role, enhancing the impact of CSR on bank stability under volatile market conditions.

Research Data and Methodology

Research Data

The study applied a panel dataset of Vietnamese commercial banks from 2010-2022. Data was collected from various sources, including bank-level data, such as financial statements, annual reports, financial explanatory reports, and sustainability reports of Vietnamese commercial banks. This data provided information on bank-specific variables such as profit, liquidity, total assets, number of branches, auditing company, bank ownership form, gender of executive, and other information (if any).

CSR Data: Information on the bank's CSR practices, including activities on shareholders, governments, customers, employees of the bank, charitable programs, donations, and other activities related to the environment, society, and community, obtained from the bank's sustainability reports and financial

disclosures and other public sources (Hair et al., 2018; Siddik et al., 2024). Green credit data: Data on the ratio of green credit loan balance to banks' total outstanding loans will be collected from financial reports, explanatory reports, annual reports, and documents submitted according to bank regulations.

Digital data: Indicators of digital transformation of banks are performed by a proxy method and measured by the ratio of investment in computer software and information technology of banks to total assets of banks; data collected from financial statements, financial explanatory statements, and industry reports of banks (Widoatmodjo & Setyawan, 2023). Our research collected 30 Vietnamese commercial banks from 2010 to 2022, which accounts for more than 97% of the banking industry's total assets. Most of the bank-specific information is taken from the Vietnamese banking database, which we collect from banks' financial statements and annual reports published annually by banks.

Research Model and Variable Measurement

The research used quantile regression using the method of moments estimation (MMQR) to capture the heterogeneous impacts of CSR, green credit, and digitalization on bank stability at different levels. Different stability. The base model can be specified as follows:

Bank Stability = f(CSR, Green credit, Digitalization, Bank-specific controls, Macroeconomic controls) (1)

From there, we built three equations as follows:

$$Bankstability_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 CSR_{i,t} + \alpha_2 SQCSR_{i,t} + \alpha_3 X_{i,t} + \alpha_4 Y_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (2)$$

$$Bankstability_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 CSR_{i,t} + \alpha_2 SQCSR_{i,t} + \alpha_3 GCR_{i,t} + \alpha_4 CSR_{i,t} * GCR_{i,t} + \alpha_5 X_{i,t} + \alpha_6 Y_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (3)$$

$$Bankstability_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 CSR_{i,t} + \alpha_2 SQCSR_{i,t} + \alpha_3 GTR_{i,t} + \alpha_4 CSR_{i,t} * GTR_{i,t} + \alpha_5 X_{i,t} + \alpha_6 Y_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (4)$$

Bank Stability

The literature shows several measures of bank stability, such as the ratio of non-performing loans and loan loss provisions to total loans (Sugihyanto, 2023), expected default risk, and bank Z-score. Since banks face different sources of risk (Chua et al., 2023), we use the Z-score as a standard measure of bank stability to capture the characteristics of various sources of risk; ZSCORE is calculated as:

$$ZSCORE_{i,t} = \frac{ROA_{i,t} + CAP_{i,t}}{\sigma_{ROA_i}} \quad (5)$$

where $ROA_{i,t}$ and $CAP_{i,t}$ are the return on assets and the ratio of total equity to total assets in year t , respectively; σ_{ROA} is the standard deviation of ROA over the examined period.

Corporate Social Responsibility

We first construct the CSR index. We categorize stakeholders into five components: shareholders, employees, consumers (depositors and lenders), government, environment, and society. The definition and calculation of each component are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Aspects that affect the social responsibility of banks

Index	Variable	Calculation
Shareholder (SHR)	Dividend payment rate	Dividend payment rate/ EPS
Employee (EMP)	Employee expense ratio	Employee expense/ total income
Customers (CUS)	Mobilization and lending expenses ratio	Expenses related to interest activities on total income
Government	Tax expense ratio and interest rate support	Tax payment amount and interest subsidy amount on total income
Environment and Social (SOC)	Proportion of welfare contributions to the environmental and social community through charity programs and social activities	Community contributions on total income

Source: The authors

Table 1 shows that most previous studies have employed content analysis and ranking indices to quantify Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). Unweighted measurement methods are used to determine the overall CSR score; however, these approaches are mainly subjective, susceptible to subjective factors, and lack objectivity. Principal component analysis (PCA) is a statistical technique that reduces data dimensionality, extracting principal components from correlated observed variables. PCA helps synthesize information from original variables and ensures objectivity in measuring complex indicators such as CSR. In this study, we use PCA to determine the weight of each CSR component, thereby building a CSR composite index that fully reflects the components of CSR in Table 2.

Table 2: The results of analyzing the main components of the bank's social responsibility

Variable	Comp.1	Comp.2	Comp.3	Comp.4	Comp.5
SHR	0.0434	0.7373	-0.1186	0.6635	0.0146
EMP	0.4559	-0.4688	0.3121	0.5375	0.4313
CUS	-0.6888	0.0290	0.0427	0.0045	0.7231
GOV	0.5536	0.2972	-0.3478	-0.4406	0.5387
SOC	0.0970	0.3838	0.8751	-0.2771	0.0269
Eigenvalue	1.9104	1.2340	0.9738	0.7082	0.1734
Proportion	0.3821	0.2468	0.1948	0.1416	0.0347

Source: The authors' process

The results of Table 2 show the individual values of each component, 1 to 5, according to the PCA method used to calculate the density for each element. The results are presented in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Weight of each component

Variable	Comp1	Comp2	Comp3	Comp4	Comp5	Fz	weight
SHR	0.0434	0.7373	-0.1186	0.6635	0.0146	0.26995	23.69%

Variable	Comp1	Comp2	Comp3	Comp4	Comp5	Fz	weight
EMP	0.4559	-0.4688	0.3121	0.5375	0.4313	0.21037	18.46%
CUS	-0.6888	0.029	0.0427	0.0045	0.7231	-0.22198	19.48%
GOV	0.5536	0.2972	-0.3478	-0.4406	0.5387	0.173413	15.22%
SOC	0.097	0.3838	0.8751	-0.2771	0.0269	0.263908	23.16%

Source: The authors' process

Table 3 presents the results from principal component analysis (PCA) showing that the proportion of CSR distributed among stakeholders in the commercial banking industry in Vietnam is as follows: responsibility to shareholders (SHR) – 23.68%, responsibility to employees (EMP) – 18.46%, responsibility to customers (CUS) – 19.48%, responsibility to the government (GOV) – 15.22%, responsibility to society, community and environment (SOC) – 23.16%. This proportion shows that the bank's responsibility to shareholders plays the most critical role in the CSR strategy of commercial banks, followed by society, community, and environment, while the government has the lowest influence.

With a weight of 23.68%, the bank's responsibility to shareholders is the most critical group in the CSR allocation of commercial banks. This reflects the bank's priority in maximising shareholder asset value and financial benefits. Banks need to ensure stable profits and transparency in operations to maintain the trust of shareholders. Shareholder benefits contribute to the organisation's sustainable development and motivate banks to fulfil long-term social commitments.

The proportion of 18.46% shows that the bank's responsibility to employees (EMP) is the second most important resource in the bank's CSR strategy. The banking industry is known to be a low-asset-intensity sector but highly dependent on human capacity. Investing in employee welfare, training, and development improves operational efficiency and enhances employee commitment and loyalty. Employees represent the brand image and are decisive in providing high-quality services, especially in digital transformation.

The proportion of 19.48% reflects the critical role of customers in implementing the social responsibility of banks. Customers, including depositors and borrowers, are banks' primary income source. Providing transparent, fair, and responsive financial products and services enhances the reputation and strengthens society's trust in banks. With a weight of 15.22%, the bank's responsibility to the government plays the lowest role in the bank's CSR allocation. This reflects that compliance with legal regulations, including taxes and other financial obligations, is a minimum and mandatory responsibility. However, government involvement through incentive policies such as green credit, interest rate subsidies, or tax incentives can motivate banks to implement CSR more effectively. The proportion of 23.16% emphasizes the bank's commitment to social, community, and environmental issues. Funding green projects, contributing to the community, and reducing environmental impacts meet social expectations and enhance the bank's reputation. Commitment to the community and environment aligns with the trend of sustainable development, contributing to building long-term trust from stakeholders.

In summary, the results of CSR allocation among stakeholders provide a comprehensive view of the CSR strategies of commercial banks in Vietnam. Commercial banks must continue prioritizing their responsibilities to shareholders, society, the community, and the environment while enhancing their

commitment to employees and customers through transparent, fair, and sustainable development policies. The role of the government should be improved through incentives such as tax incentives or support for green credit projects. Green credit (GCR): ratio of green credit balance to total outstanding loans of the bank. Digitalisation (Digitalisation – Green investment technology – GITR) is the ratio of the amount of money the bank has invested in information technology and computer software that has been accounted for as expenses over the total operating costs of the bank. Interaction variables: CSR*GCR: reflects the simultaneous impact of CSR and green credit on banking stability. CSR*GITR reflects the concurrent effects of CSR and digitalization on banking stability.

Study Results

Descriptive Statistics

Results provide descriptive statistics of the variables used in the study, including the dependent variable (Z-score), independent variables related to corporate social responsibility (CSR) and green finance, and control variables such as bank characteristics and macroeconomic factors. This analysis helps to understand the distribution and variation of variables in the study sample.

Table 4: Descriptive statistics of variables

Variables	Obs.	Mean	Std.Dev	Min	Max
ZSCORE	390	20.268	12.909	2.603	82.725
CSR	390	15.283	2.251	7.616	25.925
SHR	390	2.876	5.203	0	48.604
EMP	390	10.670	3.650	2.963	20.595
CUS	390	62.132	12.880	18.491	93.620
GOV	390	2.997	2.590	0.492	26.014
SOC	390	0.314	1.447	0	16.808
GCR	390	0.447	0.961	0	6.510
ICT	390	0.146	0.245	0	0.811
SIZE	390	5.099	0.956	2.079	7.783
BASEII	390	0.184	0.388	0	1
AUDIT4	390	0.184	0.388	0	1
CEOGENDER	390	0.848	0.358	0	1
LISTED	390	0.633	0.482	0	1
SOCB	390	0.133	0.34	0	1
COVID	390	0.148	0.356	0	1
GDP	390	6.005	2.102	2.561	8.020
INF	390	5.324	4.599	0.631	18.677

Source: The authors' process

Table 4 shows that the mean value of Z-score is 20.268, indicating that the banking system in the study sample has achieved relatively high stability. The value of the standard deviation is 12.909, indicating a significant difference in the level of stability among banks. Moreover, this variable's variation range (Min-max) is quite extensive (from 2.603 to 82.725), indicating a clear differentiation in the level of stability among banks in the sample. This shows a significant difference in the level of stability among banks. This implies that the State Bank and bank administrators need to pay attention and focus on factors that improve stability, especially for banks with a low Z-score.

The results of our baseline model

The results indicate that the CSR index has a significantly negative impact on bank Z-scores across all quantiles, suggesting that higher levels of CSR engagement are associated with lower bank stability. The impact size is relatively consistent across quantiles, with the most significant impact observed at lower quantiles. This result reflects that implementing initial CSR activities may reduce Z-score and bank stability due to high costs. This finding is consistent with the Trade-off Hypothesis of Galan and Tan (2024), which argues that CSR in the early stages increases operating costs that are not fully offset by social and environmental benefits.

The ESG activities may increase credit and liquidity risks if not managed carefully. Notably, the results report that ZSCORE has a high standard deviation and a wide range between its maximum and minimum values. To determine the normal distribution of the ZSCORE variable, the study employed the W test, a popular method for testing the null hypothesis of normality in data. The P-value from the Shapiro-Wilk test shows that the null hypothesis of the normality of Z-SCORE is rejected at a 1% significance level. This proves that Z-SCORE does not follow a normal distribution.

Table 5: The result of our baseline model

	Location	Scale	Q75	Q80	Q90	Q95
CSR	-4.360*** [-4.53]	0.034 [0.06]	-4.333*** [-3.50]	-4.321*** [-3.11]	-4.298** [-2.49]	-4.280** [-2.13]
SQCSR	12.403*** [3.77]	0.632 [0.31]	12.905*** [3.05]	13.118*** [2.76]	13.551** [2.29]	13.887** [2.02]
SIZE	-6.100*** [-5.79]	0.148 [0.22]	-5.983*** [-4.41]	-5.933*** [-3.90]	-5.831*** [-3.08]	-5.753*** [-2.62]
BASELII	1.777 [1.06]	0.796 [0.76]	2.410 [1.11]	2.678 [1.10]	3.223 [1.07]	3.647 [1.04]
AUDIT4	-4.520* [-1.81]	-3.048* [-1.95]	-6.940** [-2.14]	-7.964** [-2.19]	-10.049** [-2.24]	-11.672** [-2.24]
CEOGENDER	-2.065* [-1.67]	-0.927 [-1.20]	-2.801* [-1.76]	-3.113* [-1.75]	-3.747* [-1.69]	-4.241* [-1.65]
LISTED	0.000 [0.00]	0.000 [0.00]	0.000 [0.00]	0.000 [0.00]	0.000 [0.00]	0.000 [0.00]
SOCB	0.000 [0.00]	0.000 [0.00]	0.000 [0.00]	0.000 [0.00]	0.000 [0.00]	0.000 [0.00]
Const	92.607*** [9.68]	3.748 [0.63]	95.582*** [7.76]	96.842*** [7.01]	99.406*** [5.79]	101.402*** [5.08]

Source: The authors' process

Table 5 shows that the control variable, Bank Size (SIZE), significantly negatively impacts the bank's Z-score across all quantiles. This result suggests that a larger bank size is associated with higher operating risk and administrative costs, decreasing Z-score. The magnitude of the effect is relatively consistent across quantiles. Adopting the Basel II framework did not significantly impact the bank's Z-score across quantiles, suggesting that implementing this regulatory framework does not substantially affect bank stability. However, banks audited by one of the four largest public accounting firms were significantly associated with lower Z-scores, especially at higher quantiles. This suggests that the involvement of these firms is associated with lower bank stability, likely due to their more rigorous auditing practices.

Besides, Table 6 presents the results of using the MMQR method to examine the impact of specific CSR components, including responsibility to shareholders (SHR), employees (EMP), customers (CUS), government (GOV), and society, community and environment (SOC) on the bank's Z-score. The findings are mixed when observing CSR components; their coefficients and 95% confidence intervals are not reported here for space-saving purposes but are available upon request. The results show that the bank's responsibility to customers (CUS, CUS index has a significant negative impact on the bank's Z-score across quantiles, implying that higher responsibility to customers is associated with lower bank stability. Furthermore, the squared CUS index (SQCUS) has a significant positive impact, indicating a nonlinear relationship between customer responsibility and bank stability.

Table 6: The joint effects of CSR and green credit on bank stability

GMM-QR	Location	Scale	Q75	Q80	Q90	Q95
CSR	-4.828*** [-5.70]	0.048 [0.09]	-4.793*** [-4.33]	-4.776*** [-3.78]	-4.739*** [-2.89]	-4.714** [-2.48]
SQCSR	13.053*** [4.58]	0.307 [0.16]	13.275*** [3.57]	13.386*** [3.14]	13.623** [2.47]	13.781** [2.16]
CSR*GCR	0.825*** [3.41]	0.094 [0.59]	0.894*** [2.82]	0.928*** [2.56]	1.001** [2.14]	1.050* [1.93]
GCR	-11.009*** [-3.14]	-0.820 [-0.35]	-11.601** [-2.53]	-11.897** [-2.27]	-12.529* [-1.85]	-12.951* [-1.65]
Control Variables	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Const.	97.627*** [10.83]	4.424 [0.74]	100.82*** [8.56]	102.41*** [7.60]	105.82*** [6.08]	108.09*** [5.35]

Source: The authors' process

Table 6 shows that the coefficient of the interaction variable CSR*GCR is positive and statistically significant across all quantiles from Q75 to Q95, indicating that the combination of CSR activities and green credit can enhance bank stability. CSR can reduce the risks of green credit by improving the trust and image of banks with stakeholders. This finding supports stakeholder theory. The results argue that fulfilling responsibilities to various stakeholders, including the environment, can improve financial performance and stability.

Discussion of Findings

The research results provided the analysis findings of the simultaneous impact of CSR and digitalization (ICT) on banking stability in Vietnam. These results demonstrate the direct relationship between CSR and banking stability and clarify how digitalisation interacts with CSR to impact banking stability.

The authors find similar results to the previous analysis, a nonlinear relationship between the CSR index and squared CSR. This is consistent with strategic CSR, in which companies must balance different stakeholders' interests (Gaudio et al., 2022; Gupta & Mahakud, 2020). The results indicate that the coefficient of ICT is negative and statistically significant across most quantiles, especially strong at the lower quantiles from Q5 to Q50. This suggests that digital investments may reduce bank stability in the short term due to the high costs of technology infrastructure, software, and risk management. Banks need time to optimise these investments and improve operational efficiency (Gaudio et al., 2022; Zheng et al., 2023), who argued that the initial investment costs for digitalisation may reduce operational efficiency

and increase short-term risks but will improve risk management capabilities in the long term. Similarly, Wang et al. (2021) also showed that digitalisation increases operating costs before bringing long-term stability benefits. We conduct several robustness checks to validate the above findings. First, we measure bank stability by substituting the forward-looking z-score, emphasizing that the forward-looking z-score can better predict bank downside risk than the conventional z-score.

The results provide the analysis findings of the simultaneous impact of CSR and green credit (GCR) on banking stability in Vietnam. These results demonstrate the direct relationship between CSR and banking stability and clarify that green credit interacts with CSR to influence banking stability (Wellalage & Kumar, 2021; Tommaso & Thornton, 2020). We find similar results to the previous analysis: a nonlinear relationship between the CSR index and squared CSR. This is consistent with strategic CSR, in which companies must balance different stakeholders' interests. The results indicate that the coefficient of GCR is negative and statistically significant across all quantiles, suggesting that a higher proportion of green credit in a bank's loan portfolio is associated with lower stability. This finding contradicts the expectation that green lending activities will enhance bank stability, possibly due to the higher risks and costs related to green projects or the immature green finance market. This result is consistent with the view that green credit requires a high initial investment and has the potential for low short-term return risk. Other studies, such as Wang et al. (2023), also point out that the benefits of green credit can only be achieved when banks balance long-term risks and benefits.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Quantile regression examines the diverse effects of CSR, green credit, and digitalization on Vietnamese bank stability from 2010 to 2022. CSR has a negative impact on bank stability, while the squared CSR has a positive impact, forming a nonlinear U-shaped relationship. This indicates that the benefits of bank stability drop beyond an optimal level of CSR activity. Banks must balance CSR initiatives to maximise the financial stability-boosting effects. When studying the interaction between CSR components, it was found that shareholders, workers, customers, the government, and social responsibility have diverse implications for bank stability. A balanced CSR strategy is needed because some stability features are favourable, and others are unfavourable. The practical contribution of the study has significant consequences for politicians and bank managers:

The government should establish explicit rules and incentives for CSR adoption to balance stakeholder duties. Tax incentives and subsidies for green credit could reduce CSR and sustainability startup costs. Managers should mix CSR, green finance, and digital transformation to maximise benefits. For instance, digitalization can improve CSR reporting and green credit project resource allocation. Governance should encourage transparency, accountability, and stakeholder participation. Dedicated CSR committees and comprehensive evaluation procedures can link CSR with financial and sustainability goals. Additionally, banks should create dynamic and adaptable CSR policies that adjust to changing economic conditions like global crises without jeopardising long-term stability.

Banks should improve green project financing, as technology investments are expensive; therefore, separating green credit and digitalisation will weaken bank stability. However, merging Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) with green credit and digitalisation will improve regulation, thereby strengthening the link between CSR and bank stability. Banks could consider implementing measures concurrently to

build synergies and enhance financial stability and sustainable development. Governance should facilitate CSR, green finance, and digital transformation integration. Banks can improve financial stability by integrating CSR with green financing and digital transformation; policymakers should encourage and assist them. This could include green finance policies, credit risk assessment systems, digital infrastructure investments, and collaborative platforms for knowledge and best practices exchange.

Limitations and future research: The study only examines Vietnamese commercial banks, which may limit their applicability to other emerging or developed economies. Vietnam's legislative, institutional, and socio-economic settings may restrict the linkages' global application. Data also limits temporal coverage to 2010–2022. This era captures major trends like digital transformation and green finance uptake but may not account for long-term repercussions or post-pandemic recovery dynamics. To validate the findings and discover contextual changes, future research should compare the analysis to other locations or nations, particularly those with similar economic development. Comparative studies of emerging and developed markets may illuminate global banking stability. Longitudinal research uses a longer timescale to capture the evolution of CSR, green credit, and digitisation activities, especially as institutions optimise these methods. Finally, sectoral expansion should examine CSR, green credit, and digitalization in industry retail to determine the findings' applicability and sector-specific dynamics.

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